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IMPROVEMENT OF SURGICAL TREATMENT METHODS FOR DIFFUSE TOXIC GOITER

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Abstract. *The relevance of the toxic goiter problem is determined by the high prevalence of the disease, severity of clinical manifestations of thyrotoxicosis, development of serious complications from the cardiovascular system and other organs, as well as a significant rate of relapses after conservative and surgical treatment. Despite the achievements of modern endocrinology and surgery, the problem of choosing the optimal volume of surgical intervention, preoperative preparation and prevention of postoperative complications remains relevant. The aim of the study was to improve the long-term results of surgical treatment of patients with toxic goiter through the development and implementation of a comprehensive approach to determining the volume of operation, improving surgical technique and preoperative preparation. The work was carried out at the Department of General Surgery of Samarkand State Medical University based on surgical departments of the Samarkand State Medical University clinic and City Clinical Hospital No. 1. The results of examination and surgical treatment of four hundred ninety-eight patients with toxic goiter who were treated from two thousand five to two thousand twenty-four were analyzed. Female patients are dominated among the subjects, accounting for eighty-five percent, with a mean age of forty-seven years. The study demonstrated that a prognostically significant factor in the development of thyrotoxicosis relapse after subtotal thyroid resection is the preoperative titer of antibodies to thyroid-stimulating hormone receptors. The use of plasmapheresis in the preoperative preparation of patients with severe forms of thyrotoxicosis made it possible to achieve euthyroidism and prevent the development of thyrotoxic crisis in the postoperative period.*

Keywords: *toxic goiter, diffuse toxic goiter, surgical treatment, thyroidectomy, antibodies to TSH receptors, plasmapheresis, thyrotoxicosis, subtotal thyroid resection.*

Introduction

According to the WHO, "more than 800 million people worldwide are affected by thyroid pathology, with nodular formations accounting for 55-78% of cases(7). The prevalence of this pathology is 0.8-1.3% among men, while among women this figure reaches 5.3-6.4%, increasing to 21% in those over 50 years of age." Due to the lack of a downward trend in the number of patients and the presence of endemic regions, where the incidence rate varies from 1.1 to 8.8 per 100,000 population, thyroid diseases continue to be a serious medical and social problem, including in Uzbekistan(19). Today, "diagnosis of thyroid diseases does not present significant difficulties, largely due to the advent of non-invasive imaging methods, the information content of which, when used in combination, reaches 94-100%(9). 1. At the same time, the problem of late diagnosis and, consequently, an increase in the incidence of severe forms of the disease still persists, which significantly impacts the tactical and technical aspects of surgical treatment(9). The most common surgical method remains thyroidectomy with various options for removing varying volumes of glandular tissue (92.5%), "...however, a fairly high incidence of postoperative complications and numerous cases of postoperative relapses of the disease (13-55%), postoperative hypothyroidism (23-59%), indicate "insufficient effectiveness and reliability of the surgical tactics used..."(8).

Purpose of the studyimprovementthe results of surgical treatment of patients with toxic forms of goiter through the development and implementation of an integrated approach to determining the scope of surgery, improving surgical technique and preoperative preparation.

Material and methods

The study was conducted at the Department of General Surgery at Samarkand State Medical University. The surgical departments of the Samara State Medical University Clinic and City Clinical Hospital No. 1 served as the clinical study sites.

The work is based on the results of examination and surgical treatment of 498 patients with toxic goiter admitted for treatment to departments from 2005 to 2024.

Among 498 patients, 414 (85.2%) were women and 74 (14.8%) were men, a ratio of 5.6:1.

The age of patients ranged from 18 to 77 years, the average age was 47.2 ± 13.7 years.

Of the 498 patients with toxic forms of goiter, 204 patients had diffuse toxic goiter, 159 had mixed toxic goiter, 114 had nodular toxic goiter, and 21 had recurrent postoperative toxic goiter.

The duration of the disease before surgery ranged from 4 months to 29 years, with an average duration of 5.8 ± 4.6 years.

It should be noted that recurrent disease progression despite conservative therapy was detected in 445 (89.1%) patients, with 283 (63.9%) of these patients experiencing two or more relapses. All of these patients received long-term outpatient treatment with antithyroid drugs.

Specific complications of long-term thyrotoxicosis and long-term antithyroid therapy were identified in 397 (79.8%) patients (Table 1).

Table 1

Complications of long-term thyrotoxicosis and long-termthyreostatic therapy

Nature of the complication	Number of patients
Thyrototoxic heart	307 (61.7%)
Compression syndrome	91 (18.3%)
Endocrine ophthalmopathy	151 (30.3%)
Intolerance to antithyroid drugs	42 (8.4%)
Leukopenia	85 (16.9%)
Toxic hepatitis	7 (1.5%)

Thus, hyperthyroidism most frequently led to myocardial damage. In 153 (30.6%) patients, hyperthyroidism was associated with endocrine ophthalmopathy.

279 (56.6%) patients had severe thyrotoxicosis, which occurred against the background of an increase in the size of the thyroid gland: grade III in 249 (50.0%), grade IV in 189 (38.0%).

According to the ultrasound examination of the thyroid gland, its volume ranged from 8.4 to 295 ml, with an average of 48.9 ± 44.0 ml.

Figure. 2. Patient S., 51 years old. The echogram shows a grade IV thyroid nodule in the left lobe.

Figure. 3. Patient Sh., 51 years old. CT: Mixed goiter grade V

CT was performed to exclude malignant tumors, the presence of primary multiple thyroid lesions, and in some cases to determine indications for the strumectomy method depending on the stage of development of the pathology, localization, and nature of complications (Fig. 2, 3).

All 498 patients underwent surgery. Indications for surgery were generally accepted: failure of conservative therapy, recurrent disease, intolerance to antithyroid drugs, leukopenia, development of endocrine ophthalmopathy, development of thyrotoxic heart disease, and the presence of mechanical compression (Table 2).

Table 2

Indications for surgery

Indication	Number of patients
Tolerance to conservative therapy	42 (8.5%)
Recurrent course of the disease	446 (89.7%)
Endocrine ophthalmopathy	152 (30.6%)
Intolerance to antithyroid drugs	40 (8.1%)
Leukopenia	82 (16.6%)
Compression syndrome	90 (18.1%)

Note: 204 (81.9%) patients had a combination of 2 or more indications for surgery

Thyroidectomy was performed in 292 patients, organ-preserving surgery - subtotal thyroid resection - in 206 patients. Two main resection techniques were used: according to O.N. Nikolaev and E.A. Drachinskaya, as well as their modifications. 75 patients were operated on using O.N. Nikolaev's method. Resection of the gland modified by E.A. Drachinskaya was performed in 73 patients, combined methods (removal of one of the lobes and resection of the contralateral one according to the technique of E.A. Drachinskaya or O.N. Nikolaev) - in 58 patients. When performing subtotal thyroid resection, the volume of residual tissue ranged from 1.0 to 5.3 ml, average 3.0 ± 1.2 ml.

The distribution of patients into groups was carried out depending on the method for determining the scope of the operation.

I The comparison group consisted of consecutively admitted patients who underwent subtotal thyroidectomy with a residual thyroid of no more than 6 ml. There were 62 such patients. Immunological markers of autoimmune activity in this group of patients were not taken into account when choosing the surgical extent.

II The main group consisted of 436 patients. In this group, a differentiated approach to choosing the extent of thyroid surgery was used. All patients in this group had their TSH receptor antibody levels determined before surgery. If the TSH receptor

antibody level was below the reference value (1.5 U/L), subtotal thyroid resection was performed with preservation of the generally accepted volume of the thyroid remnant (no more than 6 ml). If the TSH receptor antibody values were equal to or higher than the reference value (1.5 U/L), complete removal of the thyroid gland (thyroidectomy) was performed. A total of 144 subtotal thyroid resections in various modifications (subgroup A of group II) and 292 thyroidectomies (subgroup B of group II) were performed in group II.

Result and Discussion

In the immediate postoperative period, clinical manifestations of thyrotoxicosis resolved in all 498 (100%) patients. Four (6.4%) patients in Group 1 developed a thyrotoxic reaction in the form of tachycardia on the first postoperative day, which was treated with beta-blockers.

Various types of vocal fold mobility impairment were detected in 72 (14.5%) patients. The degree of dysphonia varied from a slight change in voice timbre to whispered speech. In 30 (6.1%) patients, phonation changes were caused by vocal fold edema. Thus, phonation changes directly related to laryngeal paresis were diagnosed in 42 (8.3%) patients. Thus, unilateral left vocal fold paresis was detected in 14 (33.2%) patients, and right vocal fold paresis in 20 (47.5%) patients. Bilateral limitation of vocal fold mobility was diagnosed in 8 (19.2%) patients, 4 of whom had adduction laryngeal paresis, which was clinically manifested by a feeling of shortness of breath. A tracheostomy was created in 2 patients after thyroidectomy due to severe dyspnea. After 14 days, the tracheostomy tube was removed. Upon discharge from the hospital, the patients had no shortness of breath at rest(16).

Total blood calcium was measured in all patients after thyroid surgery. Calcium levels ranged from 1.42 to 2.6 mmol/L, with a mean of 2.22 ± 0.19 mmol/L. Calcium values less than 2.1 were detected in 30 patients. Thus, the incidence of hypoparathyroidism in the early postoperative period was 12.0%. Clinically significant manifestations of hypoparathyroidism were observed in 50 (10.1%) patients. They received treatment with calcium supplements and active forms of vitamin D (alfacalcidol, dihydrotachysterol).

In order to determine whether the extent of surgery affects the development of laryngeal paresis and the development of hypoparathyroidism in the postoperative period, we compared the incidence of these complications by group (Tables 4, 5).

Table 4

Postoperative complications (comparison by groups)

Complication	Group I (n=62)	Group I subgroup A (n=144)	Group II subgroup B (n=292)	P
Laryngeal paresis	4 (6.5%)	4 (2.8%)	34 (11.6%)	0.079
Hypoparathyroidism	2 (3.2%)	4 (2.8%)	54 (18.5%)	0.056

Table 5

Postoperative complications (comparison by surgical method)

Complication	Subtotal resection (n=206)	Thyroidectomy (n=292)	P
Laryngeal paresis	8 (3.9%)	34 (11.6%)	0.036
Hypoparathyroidism	6 (2.9%)	54 (18.5%)	0.0001

Thus, when comparing the incidence of complications in patients in Group I and patients in subgroups A and B of Group II, no statistically significant differences were found ($p > 0.05$). However, when comparing the incidence of complications between different surgical techniques, it was found that laryngeal paresis and hypoparathyroidism developed significantly more frequently during thyroidectomy ($p = 0.036$ and 0.0001 , respectively). There were no deaths in the early postoperative period.

All 292 patients who underwent thyroidectomy (subgroup B, group II) were expected to develop persistent hypothyroidism in the postoperative period. All were prescribed L-thyroxine at a calculated dosage of 1.6 mcg/kg body weight, taking into account age and concomitant cardiac pathology. The dosage ranged from 50 to 150 mcg, with a mean of 80.5 ± 21.3 mcg. All patients after subtotal thyroidectomy (62 patients in group I and 144 patients in subgroup B, group II) were discharged without hormone replacement therapy.

Long-term outcomes were monitored in 62 (100%) patients in Group I for periods ranging from 1 to 8 years. The analysis of long-term outcomes primarily focused on hormonal levels (TSH and free T4), thyroid volume and structure ultrasound data, and the incidence of persistent postoperative complications (hypoparathyroidism and laryngeal paresis).

In the late postoperative period (up to 1 year), low TSH levels were detected in the blood of 6 patients (9.7%), which allowed the diagnosis of recurrent thyrotoxicosis. Hypothyroidism developed in 58.2% of patients, while the remaining patients (32.3%) were found to be euthyroid.

During 1 year of observation, blood calcium levels ranged from 2.05 to 2.4 mmol/L, with an average of 2.29 ± 0.61 mmol/L. In 2 patients with transient

hypoparathyroidism, calcium levels returned to normal, while clinical manifestations of hypoparathyroidism were absent.

Also, within six months, restoration of vocal fold mobility was noted in two patients with laryngeal paresis. Thus, persistent hypoparathyroidism was not present in either patient. Six months after surgery, two patients still had laryngeal paresis.

During further observation for periods ranging from 1 to 8 years, hyperthyroidism was detected in 4 more patients. Thus, the recurrence rate of the disease over the entire observation period in Group 1 was 16.2%. The TSH level in 5 patients with recurrent thyrotoxicosis ranged from 0.0001 to 0.02 $\mu\text{U/ml}$, with an average value of $0.033 \pm 0.045 \mu\text{U/ml}$. When studying free T₄, this indicator ranged from 17.1 to 36.7 pmol/l, with an average of $25.8 \pm 7.3 \text{ pmol/l}$. Clinical manifestations of thyrotoxicosis were detected in 6 patients, including moderate tachycardia in 2 patients and no clinical manifestations of hyperthyroidism in 2 patients. All 10 patients in Group 1 with recurrent thyrotoxicosis in the late period were given indications for surgery. Six of them underwent repeat thyroidectomy. Four patients refused surgery. Two of them are currently taking antithyroid medications and beta-blockers, and two have undergone radioactive iodine therapy(15).

Euthyroid state was diagnosed in 12 patients (19.3%) aged from 1 to 6 years. Their TSH level ranged from 1.9 to 3.8 $\mu\text{U/ml}$, with an average of $2.99 \pm 0.8 \mu\text{U/ml}$. Free T₄ ranged from 12.9 to 16.5 pmol/l, with an average of $14.4 \pm 1.7 \text{ pmol/l}$. They did not receive L-thyroxine replacement therapy.

Hypothyroidism was diagnosed in 40 (64.6%) patients. TSH levels ranged from 4.89 to 8.3 $\mu\text{U/ml}$, with a mean of $6.14 \pm 1.02 \mu\text{U/ml}$. All patients with hypothyroidism were prescribed L-thyroxine at a dosage of 25 to 75 mcg.

The development of persistent laryngeal paresis was observed in 2 patients (3.2%). Calcium levels were normal in all patients. No patient developed persistent hypoparathyroidism in the long-term follow-up.

In Group 1, 52 patients (83.9%) had no evidence of thyrotoxicosis recurrence, and there were no postoperative complications. Thus, good long-term results were achieved in 83.7% of patients. Unsatisfactory treatment results were observed in 12 patients (19.6%), as 10 of them developed a relapse, and 2 patients were diagnosed with persistent postoperative laryngeal paresis.

Remote results were monitored in 424 (97.2%) patients of group II for periods ranging from 1 to 6 years. After subtotal thyroid resection (subgroup A of group II), the results were studied in all 144 (100%) operated patients, and after thyroidectomy (subgroup B of group II) in 280 (95.9%) operated patients.

In the long-term period, all patients were examined after subtotal resection of the thyroid gland.

The following results were obtained during the study of the thyroid status: 34 patients (23.6%) were diagnosed with euthyroidism, they did not receive replacement therapy with L-thyroxine, 110 (76.4%) were diagnosed with hypothyroidism. Moreover, manifest hypothyroidism with clinical manifestations was detected in 74 (51.4%) patients, subclinical hypothyroidism was detected in 36 (25%). However, severe forms of hypothyroidism were not observed. It should be noted that approximately half of the patients (48.6%) did not require hormone replacement therapy. 34 patients were euthyroid, 36 were diagnosed with a moderate increase in TSH levels and normal free T4 values. Moreover, clinical manifestations of hypothyroidism were absent. Relapse of thyrotoxicosis was not observed in any patient(14).

In a long-term study, the titer of AT rTSH in all 144 (100%) was less than 1.5 U/L.

Table 6

Comparison of surgical outcomes after subtotal thyroid resection

Exodus	Group I (n=62)	Group II subgroup A (n=144)	P
Hypothyroidism	40 (64.6%)	110 (76.4%)	0.23
Euthyroidism	12 (19.3%)	34 (23.6%)	0.79
Relapse of thyrotoxicosis	10 (16.1%)	0 (0%)	0.0019

When comparing the long-term results, it was found that the incidence of hypothyroidism in both groups did not differ statistically significantly ($p = 0.23$). The stability of the achieved euthyroid state without hormone replacement therapy in the study was 19.3% in patients of group I and 23.6% in patients of subgroup A of group II; we did not obtain statistically significant differences ($p = 0.79$). However, in group I, there were 10 patients (16.1%) with a relapse of the disease. In subgroup A of group II, relapse of the disease was not detected in any patient. Thus, the incidence of thyrotoxicosis relapse in both groups had a statistically significant difference ($p = 0.0019$).

A comparison of the long-term treatment results after performing thyroidectomy in patients of group I and group II (subgroup A) was carried out from the standpoint of evidence-based medicine (Table 7).

Table 7

Evaluation of long-term results after subtotal thyroid resection surgery

Results	Group I (n=62)	Group II subgroup A (n=144)	P
Good ones	50 (80.4%)	140 (97.2%)	0.008
Satisfactory	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1.0
Unsatisfactory	12 (19.6%)	4 (2.8%)	0.008

Thus, the conducted analysis of the obtained long-term results indicates that subtotal thyroid resection in patients with the titer of antibodies to TSH receptors below the reference value (<1.5 U/L) does not lead to a relapse of thyrotoxicosis in the late period (the differences are statistically significant, $p=0.0019$). Moreover, the development of a hypothyroid or euthyroid state does not depend on the level of AT rTSH (the differences are statistically insignificant, $p>0.05$). There were significantly more good long-term results in subgroup A of group II ($p=0.008$, the difference is statistically significant).

All 280 patients followed after thyroidectomy received L-thyroxine hormone replacement therapy in the late follow-up period. Dosages ranged from 50 to 150 mcg, with a mean of 86.3 ± 24.8 mcg. Hormone replacement therapy was adjusted based on TSH and free T4 levels, patient age, and the presence of concomitant cardiac pathology.

A 3-month thyroid status assessment revealed that hypothyroidism was compensated in 180 (64.3%) patients. Drug-induced thyrotoxicosis was detected in 22 (7.9%) patients, with TSH levels closer to the lower limit of normal ($0.4 \mu\text{U/ml}$) or less. Uncompensated hypothyroidism was detected in 78 (27.8%) patients. All 99 (35.7%) patients with decompensated thyroid function underwent L-thyroxine dosage adjustment.

When examining patients 1 year after surgery, hypothyroidism was compensated in 214 patients (76.4%), 52 (18.6%) had clinical and laboratory signs of hypothyroidism, and 14 (5%) were diagnosed with drug-induced subclinical thyrotoxicosis. Replacement therapy was adjusted in 66 (23.6%) patients.

A study of the thyroid profile in patients 2 to 6 years after surgery showed that hypothyroidism compensation was achieved in 246 (87.8%) patients, drug-induced thyrotoxicosis was detected in 8 (2.9%) patients, and a hypothyroid state was detected in 26 (9.3%) patients. Thus, target thyroid hormonal levels were not achieved in 34 (12.1%) patients in the late period. When studying the causes of inadequate correction of postoperative hypothyroidism, it was found that 10 (3.6%) patients did not comply

with the L-thyroxine intake regimen, and 24 (8.5%) patients did not have the opportunity for regular monitoring by an endocrinologist(14).

In the long-term period (more than 1 year after surgery), specific postoperative complications following thyroidectomy and subtotal thyroid resection were studied. The results are presented in Tables 8 and 9.

Table 8

Postoperative complications in the late period (comparison by groups)

Complication	Group I (n=62)	Group II subgroup A (n=144)	Group II subgroup B (n=280)	P
Laryngeal paresis	2 (3.2%)	2 (1.4%)	10 (3.6%)	0.663
Hypoparathyroidism	0 (0%)	2 (1.4%)	20 (7.1%)	0.169

Table 9

Postoperative complications in the late period (comparison by surgical method)

Complication	Subtotal resection (n=206)	Thyroidectomy (n=280)	P
Laryngeal paresis	4 (1.9%)	10 (3.6%)	0.37
Hypoparathyroidism	2 (0.97%)	20 (7.1%)	0.018

When comparing the incidence of persistent postoperative complications between the comparison group and subgroups A and B of Group II, no statistically significant differences were found ($p>0.05$). A comparison of the incidence of postoperative complications between different surgical techniques showed that persistent hypoparathyroidism develops significantly more frequently after thyroidectomy ($p=0.018$). The development of laryngeal paresis does not depend on the extent of the surgery ($p=0.36$).

Thus, in subgroup B of group II, 254 (90.7%) of the monitored patients achieved good results (no persistent postoperative complications). Unsatisfactory results were observed in 26 (9.3%) patients, who showed signs of laryngeal paresis and hypoparathyroidism in the late period.

A comparison was made of good, satisfactory and unsatisfactory long-term results of surgical treatment in patients of group I (without an individualized approach) and group II (individualized approach) using evidence-based medicine criteria (Table 10).

Table 10

Evaluation of long-term results of surgical treatment

Results	Group I (n=62)	Group II (n=424)	P
Good ones	50 (80.6%)	394 (92.9%)	0.03
Satisfactory	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1.0
Unsatisfactory	12 (19.4%)	30 (7.1%)	0.03

In Group I, good long-term results were achieved in 80.6% of patients, compared to 92.9% in Group II. A statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) was found in the comparison. Thus, the relative risk reduction for adverse outcomes from using a combined approach when choosing the surgical scope in patients with DTG was 63.4%. The relative benefit from using a differentiated approach in Group II patients was 15.2%.

Conclusions.

1. A preoperative TSH receptor antibody titer equal to or above the normal range (reference value 1.5 U/L) is a significant prognostic factor for the development of thyrotoxicosis recurrence after subtotal thyroidectomy. A high direct correlation was found between the rTSH antibody level and the development of disease recurrence ($+0.715$, $p < 0.05$).

2. In patients with DTG, the level of TSH receptor antibodies should be used as a criterion for choosing the surgical extent. Patients with elevated TSH receptor antibodies (≥ 1.5 U/L) should undergo thyroidectomy, while patients with low levels of autoimmune stimulation (< 1.5 U/L) should undergo subtotal thyroidectomy. This approach reduces the relative risk of adverse outcomes by 63.4% and increases the relative benefit by 15.2%.

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